

Evolution of *Brettanomyces bruxellensis* during secondary fermentation of sparkling wines and counteraction strategies.

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Supplementary materials

Figure S1. Chromatogram and mass spectrum of 6-Acetyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyridine (ATHP), the principal compound responsible for the ‘mousy’ off-flavour in wine.

Table S1. MRM transitions and collision energies for ATHP and pyridine.

Compound	Precursor ion (m/z)	Product ion (m/z)	Transition type	Collision energy (eV)
ATHP	125	82	Quantifier	10
	54	54	Qualifier	5
	82	55	Qualifier	5
Pyridine	125	83	Qualifier	5
	79	52	Quantifier	15